

Peculiarities of organization of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in Kharkiv

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This work is actual due to rapid growth of the popularity of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv. Identification of organizational reserves in non-Olympic propaganda system of sports in the city of Kharkiv and identification of areas of its improvement is aimed at the development of non-Olympic movement in the city.

Purpose: definition of features and ways to improve the system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv.

Material & Methods: during the research a set of scientific methods was used: Analysis of literary sources; Analysis of documentary materials; Analysis of Internet resources; System analysis; Organizational analysis; Survey (questionnaire), methods of mathematical statistics. In a study coaches and clients of fitness clubs in Kharkiv and students of Kharkiv state academy of physical culture who are involved in non-Olympic sports (n=50) participated.

Results: a system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv from the perspective of a systematic approach is characterized. Analyzed local promoter activity of management of the State's authority s in the sphere of physical culture and sport, the Federation and the other sports organizations of non-Olympic sports. The regional mass media have been identified, which cover information on non-Olympic sports. Organizational reserves are revealed.

Conclusions: the propaganda system of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv is characterized by its singularities in use of existing forms and means of propaganda in the existing resource provision and in regional media. Directions of improving the system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv are offered.

Keywords: system, reserves, directions, improving, activities.

Introduction

The modern practice of functioning and development of non-Olympic sports, as well as its social importance, are subjects of scientific interest. The need to research various aspects of system of non-Olympic sports is pointed by researches of scientists [5]. So far, in the literature the authors have presented the historical aspects of the emergence and development of non-Olympic sports, organizational and legal bases of non-Olympic sports regulation in the world and in Ukraine [8]. N. G. Dolbysheva & E. Yu. Savaretz analyzed the main directions of activity of controls authorities that provide non-Olympic sports in Ukraine [4]. Actual problems and prospects of development of strategy of non-Olympic sports in Ukraine are presented in works [9; 11].

In official documents which regulate the sphere of physical culture and sport, it is emphasizes that the first important task is forming in the population needs to systematic physical culture and sports. This underlines the great importance of propaganda in the development of non-Olympic movement. In domestic literature [3; 12] and foreign authors [13; 14] the role of propaganda and influence of the media on the devel-

opment of sport, in particular the impact of social networks on sports sponsorship and marketing are examined [17; 20; 21].

In works of some authors [1; 3; 6; 10; 12] the beginning of solution of studied problem has been started. In particular: study by A. A. Tomenko related to the study of non-Olympic sports' coverage of issues in the domestic media [12]. S. A. Stadnik & M. A. Skrinnik characterized regional media as propaganda sources of non-Olympic sports [10]. Yu. N. Zhdamirova & I. V. Petrenko considered mass physical culture and sports activities that take place in the city of Kharkiv [6]. A. Yu. Aghyppo & A. S. Bondar presented sports and recreational sports organizations in Kharkiv [1]. A. S. Bondar & V. S. Mamay especially paid attention to the lighting of Olympic and non-Olympic sports on the Internet [3]. At the same time, there are unresolved questions of the functioning and science provement of organization of propaganda for the development of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv.

Studying the system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv with the system approach aimed at identification of its characteristics and organizational reserves. This

will provide an opportunity to identify areas for improvement of the existing non-Olympic sports promotion system that will contribute to the development of non-Olympic movement in the city of Kharkiv.

Purpose of the study: to define the features and directions of improvement the system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv.

Material and Methods of the research

Participants. Coaches and clients of fitness clubs in Kharkiv (n=29), as well as 3d-grade students of the Kharkiv state academy of physical culture, involved in non-Olympic sports (n=21), took part in the study. 50 people were interviewed, 58% of them men and 42% women. The average age of respondents was 21–30 years – 58%, the maximum 41–50 years – 16%, the minimum – up to 20 years (4%). All respondents are involved in non-Olympic sports and have lived in the city of Kharkiv for at least 5 years. All participants gave informed consent to participate in this survey.

Organization of research. In order to identify the state of development of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv, as well as to determine the content of propaganda of activity, methods of analysis of legal documents and analysis of Internet resources were used. The method of system analysis made it possible to determine the structural characteristic of the system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv. Application of the method of organizational analysis made it possible to identify organizational reserves. The survey was conducted in the form of a questionnaire in order to identify the opinion of Kharkiv inhabitants as for organization of propaganda of non-Olympic movement in the city of Kharkiv.

Statistical analysis. Excel program was used in the study.

Results of the research

In our study "a system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports", was seen as a set of interrelated or interacting elements which common goal is to convince the population of the city of Kharkiv in the use and need of training non-Olympic sports. It is found that the propaganda of non-Olympic sports system consists of the external environment, input, output and feedback of the final result of the system.

The external environment is a combination of factors that influence propaganda activities. Joining to non-Olympic sports propaganda is propaganda subjects, which we conventionally combined into 3 groups. This element, influenced by the external environment, using forms and means of propaganda, existing resources, regional media, influence the object of propaganda with the aim of achieving the final result at the output. Usage of a systematic approach requires a feedback to determine the importance of the processes in the operation of the system.

Local authorities in the city of Kharkiv, presented by the Department of Family, Youth and Sports of the Kharkiv City Council (hereinafter – the Department) and its structural divisions: Management and marketing department in the field of sport; Management department of physical culture and sports; Management Investment Development and image projects, as well as the Committee on the Family, Youth and Sports in the 9 districts of the city.

Objectives and activities of the Department and its business units, aimed at promoting sports movement, including non-Olympic sports are identified. These are tasks of organizing and carrying out and, taking into account the complex market research, large-scale sporting events, as well as their promotion on the Internet, in regional, national and international media.

It was found that the Department held in the city every year image sports events on the development of non-Olympic view s sports festival of extreme sports; social project "I can"; Martial arts festival; Sports fair "Kharkiv – the sports capital"; Festival on intellectual sports "Intelliada"; Sports corporate tournament "The Battle of Corporations"; Competition "Sports initiatives of Kharkiv". The results of the survey give grounds to assert that the above mentioned image-sports events rise interest in the city's population. In particular, 66% of respondents would like to become a part of such events.

The analysis of calendar plans of the Administration of Physical Culture and Sports Department has shown that each year the city hosts about 300 sports events. Out of them, 60% are activities of non-Olympic sports. In the course of our survey it is revealed that the majority (66%) of respondents are interested in sports events that are held in the city on the power non-Olympic sports (weightlifting, arm sport, bodybuilding, power lifting, strongman).

At the same time, the analysis of propaganda activities of local government authorities in the field of Physical Education and Sports has revealed the organizing reserve. This project of the city target complex program to promote non-Olympic sports in the regional media, coordination and control over the implementation of which is entrusted to the Department of Family, Youth and Sports of the Kharkiv City Council and its structural divisions.

To public sports organizations which develop non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv, we attribute the federation of non-Olympic sports and sports society. It was revealed that currently in Kharkiv there are 65 regional and city federations of non-Olympic sports. As our research has shown, the federation promotes sport through sports events, championships, cups; participation in national and international competitions in sports and public events that take place in the city, in the country; establishing contacts with different levels of government, educational institutions, businesses, institutions; Organization and holding of meetings with successful sportsmen, coaches, sports functionaries of the federation on the basis of educational institutions of all levels, enterprises, institu-

tions; Production and distribution of booklets, posters, banners, brochures, leaflets; placing news reports and interviews in the media, creating websites or pages on social networks and others.

In addition to sports federations in Kharkiv, popularization of non-Olympic sports makes Kharkiv regional organization of sports society "Dynamo" (the FSS "Dynamo"). The analysis of schedules of fitness and sports activities of FSO "Dynamo" during 2013–2016 years has shown that the city annually held championships "Dynamo" according to the program of complex competitions "Dinamiada", "Olympics" and "Olympics-Health" in non-Olympic and professional kinds of sport.

The results of the survey show that in the city of Kharkiv, according to the respondents, mostly develop various non-Olympic kinds of martial arts (84%), as well as such non-Olympic sports such as bodybuilding (66%), power lifting (58%), fitness (50%). This is ensured by the operation of private sports schools of martial arts, fitness-clubs, fitness centers, etc.

It was revealed that today in the city operates 145 fitness clubs, 37 CYSS of state, communal property forms, as well as sports and subordinate companies and agencies. The number of pupils there is 62789. CYSS of the city cultivate 14 non-Olympic sports.

In Kharkiv regional high school of physical training and sports, along with sport reserve, training of Olympic sports branch in chess is functioning.

Kharkiv is also known for the development of non-Olympic kinds of sports as rugby league. First of Rugby League team "Legion XIII" (rugby-13), was created precisely in Kharkiv in 2006.

The study showed that in the city extreme sports are also developing on the basis of Kharkiv flying club named after V. S. Grizodubova, climbing club "Format", and mountaineering club, rollerblading "Ya-roller", Kharkiv regional hang gliding club, "Pioneer" Karting Club, "Leader", "Metallist", "Duffy", skate park. However, as the results of our survey showed, only 16% of respondents noted that they happily spend their free time skipping with a parachute, or doing sports tourism, paintball, carting.

Active rest of residents and visitors of the city is provided by functioning squash courts, a bowling club s, x Billiard clubs, paintball Cloud b on in. For example, a petanque club "Fair Play", Ukraine's only golf resort "Superior", sport-shooting club "AFAR-Ukraine". These are non-state actors that have a population of paid sports and health services, and realize boiling its activities through its own commercial and business activities.

An important element of our propaganda system is the regional mass media (mass media). In our study, there are defined 6 radio stations, 10 newspapers and magazines, 15 television channels as well as Internet resources, which provide

information of non-Olympic sports. Identified organizational reserve, this is the creation of specialized regional media for non-Olympic sports (television or internet channels, telecast, website, magazine or newspaper), substantial part of which will be not only informative and advertising, but also cognitive, analytical. Another organizational reserve is the organization of trainings for workers of federations and other organizations of non-Olympic sports to create effective advertising and administer their own Internet sites.

During the study, the respondents' assessment of the organization of the propaganda of non-Olympic sports in Kharkiv was revealed. In particular, 50% of respondents rated the level of the organization as low and the remaining 50% as average. In our opinion, such assessment demonstrates the need to activate the organizational reserves, identified by us in the activities of state and public authorities, sports and sports organizations, regional media on the promotion of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv.

Conclusions / Discussion

The modern practice of functioning and development of non-Olympic sports necessitate conducting of integrated research in order to identify trends in the formation of new concepts and developing innovative technologies to ensure the organizational and management system of non-Olympic sport. We share the opinion of M. Dutchak & N. Dolbysheva [5] that among the prospective areas of research of problems of features of development of non-Olympic sports important place is occupied by analysis of local executive bodies and public organizations of physical culture and sports orientation.

In our study, propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv was first considered from the perspective of systematic approach. The system approach in the field of physical culture and sports, according to N. V. Zhmarev [7] represents a methodological scientific approach aimed at identifying the elements of the system and analyze the interrelationships between them. Using the systematic approach to the study of the organization of promotional activities for the development of non-Olympic sports, we believe it is appropriate, as the system is social, artificial and open.

Previously, foreign authors considered the planning and management of sports events [15; 18; 19] It has been suggested [4] that, among the main directions of activity of state and public governing bodies ensuring the development of non-Olympic sport, are the preparation and conduction of competitions of various levels. Our research supplements existing data of the functioning and characteristics of the activities of state and public authorities in the field of physical culture and sports in the aspect of organizing propaganda of the development of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv.

The obtained results of the research confirm city's normative and programmatic documents, in particular, that the government bodies of the city of Kharkiv develop the sphere of physical culture and sports as a priority, having a strategic direc-

tion. Our data supplement the results of the study, which are outlined in the work of Yu. N. Zhdamirova & I. V. Petrenko [6], concerning the activities of the Department of Family, Youth and Sports of the Kharkiv City Council as for the organization and holding of sports and mass image events.

Our research suggests that non-Olympic sports are fashionable and necessary for health promotion. This is the opinion of all 100% of respondents from Kharkiv and a number of researchers of the problems of development of non-Olympic sport in Ukraine [2; 8]. However, the results of the poll contradict the author's statement [1] that in the city of Kharkiv extreme popularity, especially among youth, is acquired by extreme non-Olympic sports. In particular, the majority of respondents (84%) did not organize their active recreation in the city using extreme sports.

An important role in the promotion of non-Olympic sports is played by the media. Previously A. A. Tomenko pointed out that in Ukraine there are no specialized printed publications on non-Olympic sports. Our data supplement already existing data [12; 16]. In particular, we analyzed Kharkiv regional mass media (radio stations, print media, television channels, Internet resources) regarding the presentation of information about non-Olympic kinds of sport.

The results of our survey, as well as works [3; 10], show that Internet resources, including social networks, are the most popular among regional media [17; 20]. It was found out that the sports portal "Sports Kharkiv" has a special value in covering the non-Olympic sports in the city in terms of the number of views per day. For a day, this site has 2,732 views, for the month 81,960, and for a year almost a million – 997,180 views.

In the regional normative and programmatic documents aimed at the development of the sphere of physical culture and sports, it is emphasized that all necessary conditions are created in the city to strengthen the health of the population. This position is only half confirmed by our studies in terms of the created conditions in the city for practicing non-Olympic sports. So 58% of respondents think, and the remaining 42% – adhere to the opposite point of view. According to 50%

of respondents, it is necessary to strengthen the promotion of non-Olympic sports in the city. In our opinion, these respondents' answers give grounds to talk about improving the organization of the propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city.

This study confirms the practical recommendations and suggestions of scientists engaged in studying the problems of development of non-Olympic sport [5; 8; 9; 11]. Our study also complements the above directions. For the first time, organizational reserves were identified in the existing system of propaganda of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv.

Thus, the organization of the promotion of non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv has its own characteristics. Kharkiv is known for annual sports events of non-Olympic sports: festivals and extreme sports, martial arts, intellectual sports of the "Intelliada", etc. It is confirmed that the propaganda and development of the non-Olympic movement in the city is ensured by the functioning of local state government bodies, 65 regional and city federations of non-Olympic sports, FSO "Dynamo", 37 sports schools, 1 physical education college, 145 fitness clubs, teams of Rugby League "Legion XIII", flying club named after V. S. Grizdubova, 4 carting clubs, the only golf resort in Ukraine "Superior", etc. The results of our study indicate the need to improve the system of promoting non-Olympic sports in the city.

Based on the identified organizational reserves, we consider it expedient to propose directions for improving the system of promoting non-Olympic sports in the city of Kharkiv. Firstly, comprehensive coverage of various aspects of non-Olympic movement in regional media by creating specialized printed publications, television and radio programs, portals, Internet sites, etc. Secondly, the optimization of the management of non-Olympic sports by local government authorities through the development of the city's targeted integrated program for the promotion of non-Olympic sports in regional media. Thirdly, the development of the activities of federations and other organizations in non-Olympic sports was for attracting sponsors, popularizing non-Olympic sports by organizing and conducting trainings on creating effective advertising and administering their own Internet sites.

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